

Isothermal Coupled Transport Process across Clay Membrane

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Isothermal coupled transport of aqueous solutions of HCl, NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂ and CaCl₂ across H-bentonite membrane was studied at 35 and 40°, and the respective reflection coefficient (σ) values were evaluated. The results are explained on the basis of exchangeability of cations of the aqueous chlorides studied with H⁺ ion on the bentonite membrane phase.

SIMULTANEOUS movement of salt and water in soil and clays is of interest from theoretical viewpoint as well as from practical consideration. The study of such processes is relevant in regard to desalination, leaching, nutrient movement, evaporation as well as tracing the underground water reserves. Kemper *et al.*¹ demonstrated that the salt accumulation at the surface regulated the evaporation rate from soil. Soil salinity is also expected to be sensitive to the soil-water-plant relationships. Indeed, the salt concentration gradients may greatly affect water movement in soil. The exact mechanism through which these regulations operate may be rather intricate and varied and hence a mechanistic approach to the problem may prove too complex. On the other hand, thermodynamic approaches are reasonably independent of the structural details of the diffusing medium, but at the same time, lead to important parameters sensitive to the nature of above interactions.

Taylor and Cary² successfully demonstrated the usefulness of non-equilibrium thermodynamics in the study of coupled (mostly thermally induced) transport processes in soil systems. Subsequently, many workers² have also examined similar systems under isothermal conditions. Sanyal and associates³ have closely examined the phenomena of thermal diffusion and thermoosmosis across soil-clay systems. In this paper, we propose to have a look at the coupled isothermal transport process occurring across a clay membrane. As in our earlier investigations with the thermally driven processes, here also the attention will be primarily on the qualitative aspects.

Theoretical relations: The dissipation function (ϕ) for transport across a clay membrane separating two aqueous solutions having different concentrations that permit an osmotic flow with a concomitant build-up of hydrostatic pressure difference may be expressed as⁴

$$\phi = J_v \Delta P + J_D \Delta \pi \quad (1)$$

where, the difference Δ refers to those across the membrane. Indeed J_D may be regarded as that measuring velocity of the solute (V_s) relative to that of water (V_w), and hence its name, while J_v may be reduced to a velocity of the solvent (V_w)⁴, i.e.

$$J_D = V_s - V_w \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } J_v = V_w \quad (3)$$

The linear phenomenological equations⁵ are then obtained as

$$J_v = L_P \Delta P + L_{PD} \Delta \pi \quad (4)$$

$$J_D = L_{DP} \Delta P + L_D \Delta \pi \quad (5)$$

The fluxes refer to the membrane reference frame so that $J_M = 0$, identically. Here L_P is the mechanical filtration capacity of the membrane, L_D the diffusional mobility per unit osmotic pressure difference at zero hydrostatic pressure difference, L_{PD} is identified with the coefficient of osmotic flow, and L_{DP} the ultrafiltration coefficient of the membrane; both L_{PD} and L_{DP} may be positive or negative. Provided that these fluxes and forces are properly chosen, Onsager's reciprocity relations (ORR) hold good, namely in this case, $L_{PD} = L_{DP}$. By a series of transformations, it was shown⁶ that

$$\left(\frac{J_D}{J_v} \right)_{\Delta \pi=0} = -\frac{L_{DP}}{L_P} = -\frac{L_{PD}}{L_P} = \sigma \quad (6)$$

where, σ is known as the reflection coefficient for the given membrane-transport system⁶,

$$\text{or } \sigma = -\left(\frac{V_s - V_w}{V_w} \right)_{\Delta \pi=0} = 1 - \left(\frac{V_s}{V_w} \right)_{\Delta \pi=0}$$

By using equations (2) and (3),

$$\left(\frac{V_s}{V_w} \right)_{\Delta \pi=0} = 1 - \sigma \quad (7)$$

Also it follows from equation (6),

$$\sigma = -\frac{L_{PD}}{L_P} = \left(\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \pi} \right)_{J_v=0} \quad (8)$$

by using equations (4) and (5). For an ideally semi-permeable membrane, $V_s=0$ and $\sigma=1$, whereas for an open membrane, $V_s=V_w$ and $\sigma=0$.

Interesting cases where $V_s > V_w$ and σ is negative are known as anomalous osmosis, and are of significance for transport of electrolytes across charged membranes. For other intermediate membrane transport systems, $0 < \sigma < 1$. An examination of equation (7) reveals that the determination of σ for a given system is expected to lead to important information as regards the interaction of the solute and the solvent in the membrane phase and hence to the extent of the 'demixing' of the solute and the solvent in course of passage through the membranes, i.e. σ provides the measure of membrane selectivity.

In the present study we obtained such reflection coefficient (σ) for transport of HCl, NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂, and CaCl₂ for a mean concentration of 0.1 M each at two different temperatures of 35 and 40° across a bentonite membrane in the H⁺ form.

Experimental

The vertical osmotic cell used for the isothermal experiments consisted of two parts. Each solution chamber (or half-cell) was cut in a perspex block in a circular shape (dia 4.0 cm, thickness 1.2 cm). The bottom of each half-cell was closed by a octagonal perspex sheet. The membrane was attached in a circular hole (dia 0.3 cm), cut in the upper wall of the lower half-cell. A circular hole, cut in the bottom of the upper half-cell, completed the channel of contact between the solutions of the two half-cells via the membrane. Each half-cell was provided with a glass capillary tube in order to facilitate the determination of the hydrostatic pressure difference across the membrane. The flat surfaces of the two half-cells in contact (excluding the membrane area) were separated from each other by means of a fine sheet of plastic to prevent leakage, when the cell was in operation. The two half-cells were joined together by means of two small nuts screwed through the octagonal perspex sheets referred to above. The entire cell with its two parts was pressed against two wooden plates and the whole set-up was held together by a number of brass nuts and bolts screwed through the outer peripheral parts of the wooden plates, in order that air-tight condition was ensured. After filling up the two half-cell with the aqueous solutions under investigation, the osmotic cell was placed inside an air-thermostat maintained at the experimental temperature.

The refined bentonite clay (organic matter-free) was treated with dilute HCl for coagulation and washed several times nearly free of all the chlorides. The dialysed H-bentonite was finally left for 10 days with occasional stirring (final pH of the suspension, 7.5–8.5). The clay suspension was then boiled for about 5 min and slowly poured into a glass dish and evaporated carefully at 70–80°. The thickness of the membrane varied from 0.20 to 0.26 mm. The membrane thus prepared was cut into suitable sizes

(dia > 8 mm) and heated at 500° for 5 h. The heat treated membranes were then mounted in the circular hole of the membrane assembly using araldite as the adhesive, and once mounted the membranes were found to be fairly stable for osmotic measurements.

Procedure: The experiments conducted were diffusion of aqueous hydrochloric acid, potassium chloride, sodium chloride, magnesium chloride and calcium chloride across a hydrogen bentonite membrane at two temperatures (35 and 40°). The isothermal cell described above was mounted in the horizontal position with the membrane sandwiched in between the two solution chambers. The lower half-cell was filled with the desired solution with water in the upper one, taking due care to exclude any entrapped air bubble. The hydrostatic pressure difference between the two chambers across the membrane and its variations were recorded by noting the solution levels in the capillary tubes with the aid of a cathetometer. The attainment of the steady state was indicated by these solution levels reaching constant values and it usually took 3–4 h. The cell was then dismantled and the concentrations of the solutions in the two half-cells were checked by direct determinations carried out on suitable aliquots by the appropriate analytical methods. For instance, sodium and potassium concentrations were determined by using Na- and K-selective electrodes; calcium and magnesium concentrations were ascertained by means of complexometric titration using EDTA, while the neutralisation titrations were resorted to for finding out the H⁺ ion concentrations.

The osmotic pressure difference ($\Delta\pi$) and the hydrostatic pressure differences (ΔP) were next estimated from these measurements and the reflection coefficient (σ) was evaluated by using these data in equation (8).

Results and Discussion

The σ values are found (Table 1) to be very small for H-bentonite for diffusion of HCl. Because the passage of H⁺ ion across a H-bentonite membrane

TABLE 1—REFLECTION COEFFICIENT (σ) FOR TRANSPORT OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS ACROSS HYDROGEN BENTONITE CLAY MEMBRANE

Solution 0.1 M	Mean Temp. K	σ $\times 10^4$
KCl	313	5.71
	308	5.04
CaCl ₂	313	5.07
	308	4.39
MgCl ₂	313	4.86
	308	4.32
NaCl	313	4.57
	308	4.04
HCl	313	2.42
	308	2.73

should not involve any exchange, there does not seem to be any lag between the solute and solvent

flows, i.e. there is a nearly complete coupling between the total volume flux of solvent and the solute transmission, and hence σ approaches zero as discussed. For the transport of aqueous KCl, NaCl, $MgCl_2$ and $CaCl_2$ across H-bentonite membrane, however, an exchange reaction is involved causing a lag between the solute and solvent fluxes. Hence complete coupling between total volume flux and the solute flow does not occur, leading to a higher value of σ .

The relative exchangeability of a given cation (hydrated) depends on its bonding energy (on the exchanger) which, in turn, is a function of its ionic potential. This could mean a direct correlation between the exchanging power (i.e. ionic potential) of a cation on the given clay surface and the corresponding σ value. Indeed, this has been observed in the present study, and σ values exhibit the order, $\sigma_{Ca} > \sigma_{Mg} > \sigma_{Na}$. This order agrees with the earlier observations on relative replacing power of cations from clay and humic fractions⁶. However, KCl with K^+ being the least hydrated species among the cations studied, behaves somewhat differently in exhibiting a rather high σ value (higher than for even the divalent cations). This could possibly be attributed to the specific retention of K^+ ions in the bentonite membrane. However, more remains to be done before this surprising observation can be explained with a greater degree of confidence.

The σ values for Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ and K^+ increased with rise in temperature. At higher temperature, the degree of hydration of these cations

is expected to be reduced to some extent due to increased thermal motion of water molecules, thus causing an increase in their bonding energy and so also the corresponding σ values. The reverse trend is found with H^+ ions. This seems to arise from a more complete coupling between the solvent and solute fluxes at an elevated temperature and the unusual transport mechanism of H^+ ions through aqueous medium.

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